

Clean Milk Production: A Wide Role in Livestock Production & Management

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The milk quality is examined by aspects of composition and hygiene of milk, where management of healthcare, breeding, feeding, fodder production, and many such facts mainly influence the compositional quality. India stands on the first rank in milk production in the world. India contributes 20% of the total milk production in the world. The annual production of milk in India is 198.44 million tonnes (BAHS, 2020-21) with annual growth of 5.69 % over the previous year. The per capita availability of milk in the country was 176 grams per day in 1990-91 which has increased to 406 grams per day in 2020-21 whereas the recommendation of ICMR is 280 gm/day/capita. This article was conducted to know the level of knowledge and practices of dairy farmers regarding clean milk production.

Milk demand-supply		
Year	Total milk production (Million tonnes)	Per capita availability (gm/day)

2010-11	121.8	281
2011-12	127.9	289
2012-13	132.4	296
2013-14	137.7	303
2014-15	146.3	319
2015-16	155.5	333
2016-17	165.4	351
2017-18	176.3	370
2018-19	187.7	390
2019-20	198.4	406
2020-21 (Provisional)	209.95	-

(Source: Basic Animal Husbandry Statistics, 2021)

Clean milk: Milk obtained from healthy milch animal, having a normal taste, containing permissible limits of bacteria and essentially free from adulterants, pathogens, various toxins, abnormal residues, pollutants, and metabolites, such milk is called as clean milk.

Clean milk production and its importance: milk is normally sterile when it comes from udder of healthy animal. It is highly nutritious and contains protein, lipid, lactose, mineral etc. due to its susceptibility to microbial as it serves as an ideal medium for rapid proliferation of harmful micro-organism. Therefore, there is need to protect it from all possible sources of contamination.

Sources of milk contamination: milk contamination can be broadly categorized into internal and external factors.

Internal factors

- Udder mastitis or udder tuberculosis can lead to contamination by several micro-organism.
- Many infectious disease agents are also secreted in milk when animal get diseased with them, hence to produce clean milk production it is must to maintain good animal health.
- Foremilk of animal i.e., first few streams of milk may have a higher bacterial load as a result of bacterial that enter the udder through the teats so care must be taken to discard first few milk.

External factors

- Milker hygiene is important as milker should be healthy and equally should have good habits.
- Milk storage facility and utensils should be clean and dry
- Method of milking: feed and water used in daily routine should be clean, properly stored and easily accessible to animals. Feed ingredients should be stored in moisture-free conditions and should be free from industrial and environmental contaminants, pesticides, insecticides, fungicides, fumigants, aflatoxins as well as heavy metals.
- Milking environment should be dirt/dust free and mosquito/flies free. Regular washing and cleaning of milking parlour should be done routinely with proper disinfectants.

Unwanted changes in milk by pathogens

1. *Streptococcus liquifaciens* causes rapid milk coagulation and protein decomposition at low acid levels of milk due to renin.
2. *Bacillus coagulatus* and *Bacillus collidolactis* are heat-resistant bacteria that survive in pasteurized milk and grow at high temperatures and coagulate the milk.
3. The *E.coli* bacterium creates an offensive taste and a sticky layer.
4. *Pseudomonas fragi*, *Pseudomonas fluorescense*, *Achromobacter lipolyticum*, *Achromobacter lipidus*; are bacteria that break down fats and cause undesirable colors in the milk.
5. Milk and milk products contain yeast and molds which produce acid and gas.

Benefits of producing clean milk: -

1. Protection against milk-borne diseases.
2. Safe for human consumption.
3. Better keeping quality.
4. High commercial value.
5. Helps to produce good quality dairy products.
6. Ease of transport over long distances.

Management Practices for Production of Clean Milk:

1. Dietary Management

Good nutrition affects the quantity and quality of milk. Dusty and very fine food should not be given during milking. Milch animals should be fed one hour before milking. Silage and wet crop residues should not be put at the milking site as they may give a foul smell to the milk. The animal feed should be free from anti-nutritional factors and toxins. The feed used for milch animals should be free from a fungicide, herbicide, insecticide, fumigant, heavy metals, etc. Minerals, or supplements, should be determined by the other component of the diet. Vitamin E and Selenium must be added to the feed of milch animals.

2. Habitat Management

Animal house should be ventilated. Bedding materials such as sand or sawdust should be laid in cold weather or damp or swampy floors. Wall cracks in the animal house should be filled. Tie the animals at such a distance that they cannot lick each other. Each animal should be provided with enough lodging area in the shed. The animal house should have a proper drainage system. The collection of urine in the pit should be outside the animal house. Animal dung should be collected and disposed of away from the animal home. The animal house should be cleaned daily. Before milking, the milking area should be completely cleaned.

3. Health Management

The milch animals should be regularly examined by the Veterinarian against tuberculosis and brucellosis diseases. Milking animals should be regularly vaccinated against the foot and mouth disease, strangulation disease, and brucellosis. Animals suffering from infectious diseases should be kept separate from healthy herds. Appropriate dry cow therapy should be promoted in

dairy farms. Inappropriate or prophylactic use of antimicrobial agents should be minimized. Coliform counts on bulk milk tanks should be done regularly to check for fecal contamination of milk. Animals should be sorted based on the animal body's condition score. Swelling of udders should be detected based on counting the number of somatic cells. An udder quarter is considered healthy if it has a Somatic Cell Count is less than 100,000 cells/ml and if free of mastitis pathogens.

4. Post milking care

Raw milk quality encompasses criteria relating to composition (fat, protein, lactose, milk solids etc.) and hygiene (total bacterial count and SCC). If the post milking care is not done carefully then the benefits of producing clean milk will not be available. The animal should stand for at least 15 minutes after milking. To maintain the quality of milk, it should be cooled to a temperature below 5 °C in the refrigerator as soon as early possible. The sooner it is cooled after milking, the better its quality. Cooling the milk within 2 hours of milking slows the growth of bacteria. The distribution of milk to the consumers should be regular.

Challenges in the production of clean and safe milk:

1. Lack of technical knowledge about clean milk in the farmers.
2. The specialty of Indian dairy is that most of the producers here have 1-3 milch cattle which is a village-based activity.
3. The quality of the milk produced is compromised due to the lack of adoption of hygienic milk production practices.
4. Dairy innovations are not adopted on a large scale by dairy farmers due to a lack of extension services.
5. India has a unique pattern of milk production, processing, consumption, and marketing which cannot be compared with any developed country.
6. Ignoring the pricing policy of milk in India.

Conclusion

At present clean milk production has not been fully adopted by the milk producers. Most of the farmers have a moderate level of knowledge and adoption in various aspects of the clean milk production system. There are many flaws in our management policy for clean milk production which should be considered and rectified. Efforts should be made to convince dairy farmers to adopt clean milk production. Clean milk production should be motivated through organizing

training and demonstrations at the field level. The public should be made aware of the health hazards associated with contaminated and raw milk so that consumption of unhygienic raw milk can be avoided. Local livestock development officers, livestock supervisors, and extension workers should make efforts in this direction. Also, clean milk should be marketed efficiently at a good price.